

**PEDAGOGICAL AND DIDACTIC PRINCIPLES OF DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS'
LEXICAL COMPETENCES****Odiljonova Kamola Abduvosit qizi**

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Abstract. Innovation of the educational process on the basis of innovative technologies is the effectiveness of the communication process between the pedagogue and the student in the pedagogical process, and the acquisition of the innovative content of this process. This article describes an innovative and integrated approach to the formation of lexical competence, pedagogical and didactic foundations, their results and effectiveness, and a general analysis of theoretically based approaches.

Key words: integration, pedagogy, competence, language levels, technology, theory, methodology, innovation, didactics.

Enter. The process of organizing and implementing educational activities involves the transfer of knowledge, its reception, understanding, memorization and practical application. Today, at all stages of education, special importance is attached to the introduction of new modern technologies, their effective and rational use, and the achievement of high efficiency.

Teaching with the help of modern technologies enables students to acquire scientific and theoretical knowledge independently, to form their knowledge, skills and qualifications, and on the basis of this, to form the content of students' scientific worldviews and increase their activity. It ensures the identification and realization of creative abilities, the formation of teacher-student cooperation and the achievement of a guaranteed final result, and makes the student an active participant in the educational process. It is clear from this that bringing up a generation with high spiritual and moral potential, updating their scientific outlook based on today's requirements is one of the main tasks of education.

In a broad sense, "innovation" means optimizing the educational process and increasing its efficiency by introducing innovations into the pedagogical system. Innovation is considered to be only innovations introduced into the pedagogical system with the aim of increasing quality and efficiency, taking into account its internal capabilities. By improving this system, the system of

ideas, ideas, theories, rules, forms, methods and tools related to achieving high quality and results can be accepted as pedagogical innovations.

The main part. Innovative education is such that it creates conditions for the full development of all participants who want to develop themselves, in other words, innovative education is developing and developing education. Forming students' desire to study and turning it into a skill is the main goal of all innovative education. Such an educational process implies the active participation of the student in learning activities and the development of his creative abilities.

Innovation of the educational process on the basis of innovative technologies is the effectiveness of the communication process between the pedagogue and the student in the pedagogical process, and the acquisition of the innovative content of this process. Incorporating innovations into the teaching process is understood as the result of innovation. The innovation process is considered as the development of the following three main stages:

- development of hypotheses by students;
- development of ideas in a practical way and application of innovation in practice.

The teacher's implementation of innovations and ideas in the educational system is the use of innovative technologies in teaching science.

The following stages are distinguished in the development of the innovation process:

- identifying the need for changes;
- data collection and situation analysis;
- choose an existing innovation or develop an innovation independently;
- making a decision on introduction (mastery);
- implementation, including using the innovation as an experiment;
- as a result of mastering the novelty or using it for a long time, making it an integral part of daily practice.

The main problem of using innovative technologies is to ensure the achievement of the educational goal through the development of the student's personality. In this case, it is very important for the teacher to be able to correctly choose and apply pedagogical technology suitable for the lesson [1]. Taking this into account, we developed an algorithmic map of the development of students' lexical competence:

Stage 1. Formation of skills of performing reproductive work and analysis. Organizing the learning process in the classroom and performing independent work under the guidance of the teacher.

Stage 2. Development of productive creative movement skills and independent performance of previous actions.

Stage 3. Partly - organization of research activity processes and transfer of previously mastered material to a secondary state.

Step 4. Creativity. Acquisition of new knowledge and independent study. Students will get new ideas and conclusions during the lesson. [2].

The ordered sequence of all the above stages constitutes a complete innovation cycle.

The criterion for choosing educational methods is to take into account the number of students during the lesson. If there are not many of them, then it will be possible to conduct training at an accelerated pace using active teaching methods. If there are many, it becomes difficult to manage students due to the lack of time to pay attention to each of them, and in this case, it is necessary to use interactive methods of education in groups. The great thinker Al-Farabi in his explanations of teaching methods points out that it is necessary to provide students with various knowledge, as well as to show them ways to acquire knowledge independently, and to convince them of the necessity of knowledge without a doubt.

Student cooperation in the lesson helps to increase the effectiveness of education and upbringing. "...language is not only a simple means of communication between people, but also a means for the speakers of the language to know the world around them, to pass on the acquired knowledge to the next generation. If the speaker acquires the linguistic structures, but does not know how and in which places to use them, it is impossible to think about the full ownership of the linguistic ability. Therefore, in order to educate a person with strong linguistic ability, in the educational process, the main attention of students should be focused not only on knowing the pure internal structure of the language, but also on knowing how to use each of them in which situations. [3].

Interdisciplinary communication is widely used in education. This, in turn, serves to strengthen the structural connection between subjects, to generalize them, and to further enrich students' overall vision of the subject. Practical experience shows that teachers do not pay enough attention to interdisciplinarity in the educational process. As a result, educational efficiency is not ensured during theoretical and practical training.

Currently, there are more than 30 definitions of "interdisciplinary relations" in the pedagogical literature, and there are different approaches and different classifications regarding their pedagogical evaluation. Interdisciplinarity helps to increase the scientificity and ease of teaching in relation to the teaching process, to strengthen the cognitive activity of students, to improve the quality of their knowledge, and to effectively develop the scientific views of students. Interdisciplinary integration is of great importance in discovering the roots of concepts that are close to each other in several disciplines, in studying the interaction of these disciplines and their influence on each other.

While working on the text of the work in literature classes, during the analysis of the personality and life of the hero of the literary work, the student himself enters into life and learns to understand others. By learning from others, he is formed as a person. In high school, literature is studied as a separate subject from the 5th grade. At the same time, in the period when the child is interested in everything and the desire to know the essence of everything has not faded, it is necessary to use the available opportunities to form positive qualities in him, to educate him as an independent thinker. Literature is one of the main means that elevates a person to such a rank and encourages him to be high as a person.

The effectiveness of teaching the mother tongue largely depends on its connection with literature or vice versa. In fact, mother tongue is also studied in literature classes. For example, during the analysis of the language of an artistic work, attention is paid to the stylistic significance of some grammatical forms. [4].

There are certain standards, criteria, and scientifically established rules for using the language and its opportunities. These phenomena determine the range of correct and acceptable possibilities of using the language, and it is regulated by a certain system. This, in turn, places a huge responsibility on the teachers of the native language and literature, encourages them to focus on education and introduce interactive methods, innovative pedagogical technologies and their skillful use to increase the effectiveness of the teaching process.

In the opinion of Methodist scientist T. Ziyodova: "The teacher should not limit himself to the textbook when organizing students' work on the text, but also use scientific and fiction literature, selected texts from the periodical press, audio-video tapes, the productivity of this activity, will ensure an interesting and enjoyable time for students." [5].

The degree of connection between linguistics and other disciplines varies. Only some issues of linguistics are related to some sciences. In particular, in determining the distribution areas

of linguistic phenomena with geography, in mapping these areas; studying the physical properties of speech sounds with the acoustics department of physics; the relationship between medicine and the study of speech issues is felt. As a result of interdisciplinary integration, directions between two disciplines are emerging, which, as a result of their appropriate application, can be seen as a manifestation of systematicity. Integrating education increases students' enthusiasm and interest in learning subjects, increases the level of knowledge in academic subjects, develops their mental activity, ensures the mutual, natural coherence of educational materials. provides.

In recent years, many scientists have conducted research in this field. For example: Sh. Yusupova and Rejapova conducted research on the method of organizing integrated classes, U. Musayev on the importance of integration in optimizing the educational process. O. Ghaziyeva, R. Ismailov developed various methods of using integrated education methods. [6].

The integration of linguistics with a subject means that the language is combined with certain subjects or a set of subjects of that subject and unites to form a whole concept and theory. If one subject is removed, the description of those subjects will be incomplete, incomplete, incomplete. The relevance of integration in the educational system is explained by the level of modern development of science, which clearly expresses the integration of social, natural, and technical knowledge. Applying several subjects to the educational process in interdependence increases the student's interest in science, teaches creativity, directs research, expands imagination. If he observes freely through individual thinking, he learns to understand himself and respect others' opinions in the process of working as a team. Therefore, the practical application of integrated lessons at every level of the educational system will greatly help in organizing educational activities more interestingly and in accordance with state educational standards.

Organization of integrated lessons in the course of the lesson gives effective results in solving such issues.

The method of education in general education schools is mainly cognitive-pragmatic. In this case, the student is the active participant in the lessons. Each lesson includes approximately four steps.

1. Repetition.
2. Analysis of given materials by students.
3. Summarize and judge the given materials with the help of the teacher.
4. Practical application and testing of the generated generalization, completion of educational problems.

Students' text creation and work on the text occupy a central place in the second and fourth stages of the training and in the assignments given outside the classroom. The texts are varied. Their exact type and appearance are partly given in the textbook, but mostly determined by the teacher. The program gives the teacher a full opportunity to easily replace all the texts in the textbook according to his taste, requirements, convenience to the conditions, to build the teaching process on the basis of literal creativity and research. Tasks and exercises for working on the text are given a lot of attention in these programs and textbooks.

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